

Flame retardant behavior of nitrogen and phosphorus based polymers and effect of nitrogen and antimony on their flame retardancy

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Phosphorus and heterocyclic based epoxy resins have been synthesized as comparatively more flame retardant and thermally stable polymers than commercially available bisphenol-A-epichlorohydrin standard epoxy resin. The effects of nitrogen and antimony on flame retardancy of the phosphorus-based and heterocyclic-based epoxy resin are also reported. At a particular P/N or Sb/N ratio the synergistic effect is maximum.

In order to obtain a fire proof coating and adhesive material like epoxy resin, initially the bisphenol-A moiety of the DGEBA (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A) was replaced by halogenated diols¹. But these fire retardant materials on burning, liberate harmful HX gases. In order to protect the resins from fire, suitable flame retardant additives like PPh₃², MoO, Sb₂O₃³ were incorporated into the resin system. But unfortunately all these conventional non-polymeric fire retardant (FR) additives suffer from leaching and migration from the polymer surface during the service-life of the resin, and some of them are also toxic. To develop the self-extinguishing eco-friendly epoxy resin, 0.5–1% phosphorus was incorporated in DGEBA resin system by treatment with H₃PO₄ during the curing cycle⁴. But flame retardancy of this system was not satisfactory. Recently, phosphorus based epoxy resins were synthesized from dichlorodiphenyl phosphine oxide and glycidol⁵ which showed the limiting oxygen index (LOI) value of 35 in the cured state.

The present communication reports the evaluation of flame retardancy of phosphorus and heterocyclic based epoxy resins synthesized vis-a-vis that of the standard epoxy. Attempts have also been made to study the effect of nitrogen on phosphorus and antimony in the flame retardancy behavior of the blends of epoxy resins developed in order to understand the mechanism of action.

Results and Discussion

Flame retardancy of phosphorus containing adhesives :
The phosphorus based epoxy resins have been synthesized from dichlorodiphenyl phosphine oxide and bisphenol-A, resorcinol, 4,4'-thiodiphenol, 4,4'-sulfone diphenol and epichlorohydrin.

Probable structures of resins are presented in Scheme 1⁶.

The LOI values of the polymers are shown in Table 1. The results reveal that phosphorus based epoxy resins are

Scheme 1

self-extinguishing (LOI ≥ 28) whereas commercial epoxy (Ciba-Geigy's two-pack epoxy) is not (LOI = 26.5)⁷. The LOI values of these phosphorus based epoxies range from 33.3 to 40.3. The maximum LOI value was obtained for the polymer P₂ due to its highest P content, and the minimum LOI value exhibited by P₄ due to its lowest P content. On burning it forms the phospho-ester network structure over the polymer surface that inhibits the access of oxygen to the

Table 1. LOI values of the phosphorus and heterocyclic ring containing polymers

Polymer	Active flame retardant element (wt%)				LOI value
	N	P	S	Cl	
P ₁	–	4.78	–	–	33.3
P ₂	–	7.78	–	–	40.3
P ₃	–	4.82	10.40	–	34.0
P ₄	–	4.50	9.40	–	30.0
HP ₁	7.26	–	9.48	5.19	30.0
HP ₂	8.90	–	10.00	5.62	30.0
HP ₃	9.02	–	–	–	25.0

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burning site and promotes char formation⁸. In case of polymers P₁ and P₃, containing almost the same phosphorus content, the LOI values are the same, though P₃ contains 10.4% of sulfur. Hence, chemically bound sulfur has no contribution to the flame retardancy of polymer P₃. Similar observation was also noted by other workers⁹.

However, it has been reported that sulfation of cellulose by sulfuric or sulfamic acid salt imparts flame retardancy to cellulose¹⁰. This has been explained by the fact that sulfur compounds (acid form) act on cellulose via carbonium-ion catalysis¹¹, thereby helping to liberate water molecules from cellulose. But in polymers P₃ and P₄ sulfur is not present in such acid form. Therefore, sulfur has no effect on flame retardancy of these two polymers.

Flame retardancy of nitrogen containing adhesives : The LOI values obtained for nitrogen containing polymers HP₁, HP₂ and HP₃ (Scheme 2) are also shown in Table 1.

Scheme 2

It is observed that polymers HP₁ and HP₂ show the same LOI value, as in both cases the active flame retardant elements, viz. N, S, and Cl are present almost in the same percentage (Table 1). The higher LOI values exhibited by both HP₁ and HP₂ polymers than that of commercial epoxy, are possibly due to their halogen content (~5%). The presence of halogen allows to form noncombustible HX gases which retards the burning process in these two polymers. The LOI value of polymer HP₃ is very low, almost the same as that of the commercial epoxy resin (Ciba-Geigy's two-pack). From this result it is clear that nitrogen is not a flame retardant element *per se* and fails to contribute to the flame retardancy when present alone in the polymer.

Flame retardancy of phosphorus-nitrogen blends : Investigations were made earlier to get the highest synergistic effect on flame retardancy of the phosphorus-nitrogen system¹². In this context two sets of blends were prepared. In the blend system (a), any ratio of P/N shows the synergistic effect (Table 2). However, this synergistic effect is maximum at the P/N ratio of 1.77. But in case of blend system (b), the synergism is maximum at the P/N ratio of 1.24 (Table 3). In the blend system (b) polyaromatic ring around the phosphorus in the P_x polymer prevents it from achieving physical proximity between P and N¹². Therefore, the for-

Table 2. Variation of (OI)_m with P/N ratio of P₁-HP₃ polymer blend system

P-1/HP ₃ wt. ratio	%P	%N	P/N ratio	(OI) _m obtd	(OI) _m calcd ^a	Increase in (OI) _m
7.1	4.27	1	4.27	36.6	32.3	4.35
2.54 : 1	3.54	2	1.77	40.0	31.2	8.78
1.5 : 1	3.05	3	1.01	31.6	30.0	1.60
1.1	2.40	4	0.60	30.0	29.0	1.00
3 : 5	1.83	5	0.37	35.0	28.0	7.00
1 : 3	1.22	6	0.20	30.0	27.0	3.00

^aOn the basis of additive rule. (OI)_{nc} = Σ (LOI)_iw_i, where (LOI)_i = value of LOI of i-th component and w_i is the weight fraction of i-th component.

Table 3. Results of (OI)_m of P_x-HP₃ blend system

P _x /HP ₃ wt. ratio	%P	%N	P/N ratio	(OI) _m obtd.	(OI) _m calcd ^b	Increase in (OI) _m
6 : 1	6.00	2.3	2.60	50.0	41.5	8.5
1.5 : 1	4.20	3.2	1.30	55.3	48.5	6.8
1.07 : 1	3.75	3.0	1.24	57.3	46.0	11.3
1 : 1	3.50	4.0	0.87	38.3	36.5	1.8
0.34 : 1	1.78	6.4	0.28	33.3	29.6	3.7

^aLOI value of P_x is 48. ^bAs described in Table 2.

mation of the P-N network structure is difficult over the polymer surface which is responsible for flame inhibition. This result is contradictory to earlier reported results. It was reported¹³ that the synergistic effect is not a function of any specific N-P ratio but increases with the increasing amount of nitrogen at fixed phosphorus content. Most probably this discrepancy may be due to the presence of epoxy group which opens up and helps to form the network structure as the nitrogen atom does and inhibits oxygen to come at the burning zone.

Influence of SbPh₃ and antimony polymer on flame retardancy of nitrogen containing polymers (HP₃) : The role of antimony polymer or compound on flame retardancy of nitrogen containing epoxy resins was studied by blending antimony polymer (P_{Sb}) with HP₃ in blend (c) and SbPh₃ with HP₃ in blend (d). In both cases, antimony and nitrogen

Table 4. Results of LOI of antimony polymer (P_{Sb})-nitrogen based polymer (HP₃) blend system

P _{Sb} /HP ₃ wt. ratio	%N	%Sb	Sb/N ratio	(OI) _m obtd	(OI) _m calcd. ^b	Increase in (OI) _m
0.15 : 1	7.00	2.6	0.37	28.3	25	3.3
0.35 : 1	6.00	5.2	0.86	26.6	25	1.6
0.54 : 1	5.00	7.8	1.56	33.3	25	8.3
1.08 : 1	4.01	10.4	2.60	36.6	25	11.6
1.85 : 1	3.02	13.0	4.33	33.3	25	8.3

^aLOI value of P_{Sb} is 25. ^bAs described in Table 2

Table 5. Results of LOI of triphenyl antimony (SbPh₃)-nitrogen based polymer (HP₃) blend system^a

SbPh ₃ wt. ratio	%N	%Sb	Sb/N ratio	(OI) _m obtd.	(OI) _m calcd.	Increase in (OI) _m
0.18 : 1	7.0	4.2	0.60	36.6	26.25	10.35
0.46 : 1	6.0	8.5	1.41	33.3	27.75	5.55
0.91 : 1	5.0	12.8	2.56	30.0	29.12	0.88
1.78 : 1	4.0	17.1	4.20	31.3	30.00	1.30
3.72 : 1	3.0	21.1	7.20	33.3	31.87	1.43

^aLOI value of SbPh₃ is 36.

interact with each other and increase the flame retardancy by synergistic effect. The flame retardancy behavior of blends (c) and (d) varies erratically with the Sb/N ratio (Tables 4 and 5, respectively). In blend system (c), the maximum LOI value was obtained at the Sb/N ratio of 2.6 which is 11.6 units higher than their additive values. In blend system (d), the maximum value appeared at the Sb/N ratio of 0.6 which is 10.35 units higher than their additive values. Most probably due to the high volatility of SbPh₃ it volatilizes before interaction with nitrogen. Therefore, synergistic effect is maximum at high concentration of nitrogen, i.e. at lower Sb/N ratios.

Influence of antimony polymer on phosphorus based epoxy resins: The variation of LOI with P/Sb ratios is shown in Table 6. The observed LOI values are lower than their additive values. This means that phosphorus is antagonistic to antimony in the flame retardancy of polymers. This may be due to the fact that phosphorus acts as an interfering agent with the formation of vapor of antimony compound¹⁴. Our results indicate that antagonistic effect between P and Sb in flame-retardancy perhaps does not obey any specific rule.

Table 6. Influence of antimony polymer (P_{Sb}) phosphorus based epoxy resin (P₁)

P _{Sb} /P-1 wt. ratio	%P	%Sb	P/Sb ratio	(OI) _m obtd.	(OI) _m calcd. ^a	Decrease in (OI) _m
0.13 : 1	4.3	2.3	1.85	26.6	30.30	3.70
0.17 : 1	4.2	2.9	1.40	25.0	29.28	4.28
0.8 : 1	2.8	8.9	0.31	26.6	27.80	1.20
1.08 : 1	2.4	10.4	0.23	25.0	28.30	3.30
1.45 : 1	2.0	11.9	0.16	23.0	27.10	4.10

^aAs described in Table 2.

Conclusion: The new phosphorus based and nitrogen based epoxy resins are self-extinguished. The phosphorus-nitrogen based epoxy blend system and the nitrogen-antimony based system both show a synergistic effect on flame retardancy. However, this synergistic effect varies erratically

with change in P/N ratio. Also the synergistic effect depends on the structure of the phosphorus polymer. Similarly, the synergistic effect is also noted in blend systems containing antimony and heterocyclic N-containing moiety and it varies with effective interaction between nitrogen and antimony. However, phosphorus shows an antagonistic effect with antimony.

Experimental

Triphenyl antimony (Aldrich) and acetone (s.d. Fine Chem) were used as such. Antimony polymer (P_{Sb}) was synthesized from triphenyl antimony dinitrate and disodium salt of bisphenol-A in DMAc solvent. Phosphorus based polymer (P_x) was synthesized from dichlorophenyl phosphine oxide and phenolphthalein in chloroform solvent at room temperature⁹.

All phosphorus based epoxy resins (P-1 to P-4) and heterocyclic based epoxy resins (HP₁-HP₃)^{6,16} were evaluated for their LOI values.

Preparation of blends: In solution blending, both the components dissolved in acetone were mixed in appropriate amounts such that no precipitation occurred. The mixed solution was slowly evaporated to dryness to obtain the desired blends. The following blend systems were prepared: (a) polymer P-1/HP₃ blends were prepared with different weight ratios, (b) polymer P_x/HP₃ blends were prepared with different weight ratios. Similarly polymer blends (c) and (e) were prepared with different weight ratios of P_{Sb}/HP₃ and P-1/P_{Sb}, respectively. In hot-melting technique, triphenyl antimony and polymer HP₃ (blend d) were mixed in appropriate amounts and heated to melt and mixed thoroughly by stirring. The melt was then cooled down to room temperature to produce a homogeneous blend as observed visually, and powdered finely.

The flame retardancy of the polymers and their blends was measured by determination of limiting oxygen index (LOI) according to the procedure of ASTM D 2863-77. A mixture of nitrogen and oxygen gas was allowed to pass around the sample in a carefully controlled rate to find out the minimum concentration of oxygen (by volume %) to just sustain the burning of the flame. The LOI value was calculated by the relation,

$$\text{LOI} = \left\{ \frac{[\text{O}_2]}{([\text{N}_2] + [\text{O}_2])} \right\} \times 100$$

The LOI method used for self-supporting samples was modified¹⁷ for powder or viscous samples and the values were denoted by (LOI)_m. In this experiment, polymer sample (~1.5 g) was placed in a glass cup (dia. 20 mm × 10 mm) fitted to the specimen holder. An external flame of 20 mm length was maintained in contact for 2 s with the polymer. The LOI value was taken as the minimum percentage of oxygen in oxygen-nitrogen atmosphere surrounding the sample to maintain its combustion. The LOI value of each sample was taken as the average of five replicate samples with an average experimental error of ±1.0%.

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